

Comparative Musical Frameworks: Vocal Techniques and Terminologies in Hindustani and Western Classical Music Traditions

Lavanya Gosai ^{*†} and Parul Purohit Vats^{2 ‡§}

School of Performing Arts, World University of Design, Sonapat-131021, Haryana, Bharat (India).

*ORCID:<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5090-6375>

†lavanyagosai123@gmail.com

‡ORCID:<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3359-4066>

§Preciosparul79@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Vol. 03, No. 01(2026); pp 8-16

Received : 11/03/2026

Accepted : 19/04/2026

Published Online : 01/05/2026

DOI:

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How to Cite?

Lavanya Gosai & Parul Purohit Vats (2026). Comparative Musical Frameworks: Vocal Techniques and Terminologies in Hindustani and Western Classical Music Traditions. **Green Lifestyle and International Market-(GLIM)**, 3(01), 8-16.

Abstract

Background: Music is widely known as a universal form of expression that transcends cultural, linguistic, and geographical boundaries. Although both traditions differ in their structural frameworks, philosophical foundations, geographical boundaries, they share similar musical elements, emotional expression, devotional aesthetics and artistic practices. Music enables communication across diverse societies and can bind emotional connection across distinct cultures.

Purpose: The following research presents a comparative analysis of Western music and Hindustani classical music traditions, emphasizing their theoretical and structural, framework of expression, including melody, rhythm, vocal techniques, and ornamentation.

Methods: This study conducts a comparative analysis based on scholarly sources, documented performance practices and musical theoretical frameworks. It includes raga-scale, tala-rhythm structure, vocal techniques, improvisation, case studies of selected artists and cross-cultural musical adaptation.

Results: The findings include that both traditions share same functional approaches but differ in theoretical frameworks. Western classical music focuses on harmonic organization, pre-composed compositions, linear rhythmic structures and equal temperament. In contrast Hindustani classical music is based on raga, a cyclical rhythmic framework, improvisation and a microtonal approach (shruti). Hindustani music follows monophonic pitch approach, whereas Western music focuses on harmonic pitch organization. Both musical traditions showcase parallel approaches to emotional expression.

Conclusions: The study concludes that both traditions share similar musical goals but differ in musical functionality. Further it highlights fusion practices, cross-cultural musical adaptation and innovation between traditions re-emphasizing the music is a universal medium to communication that bridges diverse traditions.

Keywords: Vocal Techniques, Western Classical Music Traditions, Musical Frameworks, Devotional aesthetics

1. Introduction

In Hindu philosophy, the concept of *Nada Brahma* signifies the divine cosmic principle. The vibrations and energies explained in science, parallel philosophical idea of *Nada Brahma*, suggesting that both traditions associate the sound as a force of creation. *AUM* or *OM* is represented as the primal sound in Hindu mythology; it highlights the idea that sound functions as both origin and symbol. This showcases how Indian traditions conceive sound as a manifestation of the divine.

The origins of Hindustani classical music can be traced to the Vedas. This highlights that they were not merely compositional systems, but that their development is deeply embedded in oral and ritualistic traditions. The Vedas are among the oldest sacred texts in the history. These texts are divided into four categories, each contributing unique purposes and aspects of Vedic knowledge. The classification of four Vedas provides structured knowledge in different areas. Among them, Samaveda is particularly significant in developing the foundation of music, as it transforms the recitation of chants into melodic structures, marking a critical shift from spoken to musical expression. The *Samaveda* showcases one of the earliest systems of musical expression, later forming the basis of the Indian classical music system.

Western classical music originated in Europe and spread widely to the Americas and other parts of the world. As early as the Medieval period, music was characterized by Gregorian chants with a monophonic texture. This demonstrated an emphasis on melodic uniformity, which later developed into complex harmonic structure. The evolution from Renaissance polyphony to the harmonic complexities of the Baroque and Classical periods showcases a gradual shift from linear to vertical musical organization. Composers such as Bach, Handel, Beethoven, Mozart, and Haydn contributed to clarity and harmonic balance. The Romantic era focused on individual expression.

Despite both traditions having extensive scholarly literature writings, limited research has been conducted nor is there a structured, balanced and comparative analysis between two systems. Examining the corresponding conceptual elements such as raga - scale, ornamentation, tala meter, improvisational elements and movement within the analytical framework, existing studies emphasize historical evolution and fusion practices. Hence this study addresses the gap by implementing the descriptive comparative methodology to evaluate functional correspondences and structural differences between two music forms.

2. Review of Literature

Music is widely recognized as a complex phenomenon, and its association with expression and spirituality varies across different traditions Rao-de Haas, S. (2022). Rao-de Haas links the origins of music to cosmic creation of the universe; however, it is primarily philosophical and contrasts with historical approach and cultural approaches. Within the Indian philosophy, this perspective is derived from the concept of *Nada Brahma*, which presents sound as the foundation of creation. This indicates that sound is not merely purely artistic but has a metaphysical framework. Sacred texts such as the Vedas, Upanishads, and the Bhagavad Gita emphasize OM as the primal sound, establishing that sound functions as both metaphysical principle and a medium of spiritual experience Beck, G. L. (2010).

The *Samaveda* holds a significant role due to its emphasis on melodic chanting (*sama*), which represents a shift toward structured musical expression. *Samagana* refers to collective chanting practices, that showcase early rhythmic development. The rhythmic chanting of Sanskrit hymns laid the foundation for later developments in the musical system. *Samagana* is associated with the *Udgatta*, the priest responsible for chanting More, S., & Anuradha, G.B.V. (2013). Scholars highlight the importance of ancient theoretical treatises such as the *Natyashastra* written by Bharata Muni, which systematically integrates music, dance, and drama, establishing a comprehensive theoretical structure. The *Natyashastra* establishes foundational principles of music theory in relation to the theoretical representations, emotional expression, and performance practices. These principles influenced the development of raga-based melodic systems and improvisational frameworks that characterize Hindustani music.

In contrast, to the foundation of Hindustani classical music, western classical music traces its origins to early European religious practices, reflecting a more institutional form of development. During the Medieval period, Gregorian chants emerged as the foundational form of Western classical music. These Monophonic chants served liturgical, devotional and purposes within religious practices. Both traditions originated within religious context; however, their evolution is distinct in structure and purpose. The emergence of polyphony marked a significant shift in western music, introducing the harmonic complexity.

3. Objectives of The Study

Based on the conceptual frameworks, objectives of this study include a comparative analysis of Hindustani classical

music and western classical music. With emphasis on their spiritual, philosophical and social-cultural foundation, this research aims to examine the historical origins and evolution of both traditions as showcased in the sacred texts, music literature and historical development.

Comparing fundamental musical elements, including melody, rhythm, tuning systems, and ornamentation in western classical music and Hindustani classical music, the study analyzes concepts such as raga and scales, tala and time signatures, with microtonal tuning and the equal temperament. Identifying key structural elements and the differences between both forms Hindustani classical music and western classical music system, the study aims to analyze the applied vocal techniques, their role shaping in vocal expression and performance practice distinctions. Understanding how Hindustani vocals correspond to the different forms or align with the western music vocal practice is one of the key reasons for the research. It includes exploring the evolution of fusion music and the contribution of selected key artists bridging Indian and Western classical traditions while also highlighting the case studies of prominent musicians, and analyzing the importance of the cross-cultural collaboration, mutual understanding, selected case studies and artistic integration in the development of fusion music. Finally examining the concept of music as a universal language, how it transcends linguistic, cultural, and geographical boundaries and summarizing with comparative findings from both traditions.

4. Scope and Limitations of The Study

The scope of this research is a comparative study of Hindustani classical music and Western classical music, with an emphasis on vocal music, musical terminology, and theoretical frameworks. The study includes historical development, melodic and rhythmic structures, ornamentation practices, and improvisation in both traditions.

Focusing on the selected artists who have played a significant role in cross-culture musical exchange, the study examines fusion music as a cultural phenomenon while understanding their musical forms.

This study is limited as it relies primarily on the secondary sources and does not include experiments, fieldwork, performance analysis, or interviews with practitioners. The focus remains on Hindustani classical music and Western music forms, with limited discussion of Carnatic music and other traditions. Additionally, the vast diversity within Western classical traditions is addressed

broadly rather than in depth. The discussion of fusion music is selective and does not include all contemporary practices.

5. Methodology

This study adopts a comparative analytical approach to examine vocal techniques and terminology in both musical traditions. This research is based on the textual analysis of established theoretical sources, scholarly writings, and documented performance practices. The comparative criteria include pedagogical terminology, ornamentation systems, improvisational techniques, structures, and the conceptual framework of expression in both traditions. The selected parameters ensure a balanced and structured analytical comparison between the two traditions. It aims to identify and evaluate structural similarities and differences within the pedagogical systems and does not attempt to establish any hierarchical comparison between them.

6. Exploring Interchangeable Elements in Hindustani and Western Classical Music

6.1 Melody: The raga / scales

Both Hindustani and Western classical music employ melodic frameworks; however, their functional principles differ significantly. In western music, the division of frequency range in an interval is known as scale. They have infinite steps for the movement and can be defined with the relation its root of the scale. It is a set of tones consisting of a definite pitch and specific intervals, relative to the other pitches. When played in sequence, the movement of frequency can be seen either rising or falling. In contrast the raga in Hindustani classical music refers to the composition solely relies upon the specific juxtaposition of notes, sounded in sequence. It includes prescribed ascending (*arohana*) and descending (*avarohana*) patterns, along with emphasized key notes, that evoke a specific emotional essence (*rasa*).

Scales differ from mode (a scale pattern organized around a specific tonic) in which they do not have a tonic note. However, scale can have different modes, depending on the notes chosen as primary. Similarly, a *thaat* is a simple organization of notes in natural sequence, whereas raga is combination of notes belongs from a particular *thaat*. This reflects that *thaat* can be associated with scales, the natural enumeration of notes like *thaat* and modes with ragas as they both have specific arrangement of notes similar to modes

in western music (Rayacaudhuri, V. (2000), Rechberger, H. (2018)).

Ragas may incorporate microtonal intervals (*shruti*) within the conventional 12-tone framework. Ethnomusicological study highlight that Western scales rely on twelve-tone equal temperament, whereas Indian music is based on whole-number frequency ratios, incorporating theoretical microtonal division Das, J (2011). This distinction reflects two fundamental contrasting musical frameworks.

6.2 Rhythm Tala and Time Signature

Rhythm plays an important role in both traditions, providing structural organization and serving as the back-bone of musical performance. Western classical music operates with time signatures such as 4/4 (common time), 3/4 (waltz), and 6/8 (compound meter) to organize beats into linear patterns. In contrast Hindustani classical music *tala* operates through cyclic rhythmic structures. These are composed of fixed beats (*matras*) subdivided into sections (*vibhags*), with distinctive markers (*sam, tali, khali*) that define the rhythmic cycle. Tala cycles can be highly complex, often extending beyond the structural limits of western time signatures. When one performs improvisation, it must begin on *sam* and can be extended over many cycles accordingly. The cyclic conception of rhythm in Hindustani classical music creates a circular return movement structure. In contrast Western rhythm is advances in a linear progression (moving forward) often driven by tension and release to achieve final resolution.

6.3 Ornamentation and Expression

Ornamentation and Expression play significant role in both traditions. In Hindustani classical music ornamentation and its components have direct link to emotional expressions. Traditional music suggests that in a raga unless *alankaras* are used, it will not possess color and effectiveness to evoke emotional expressions. To characterize a raga, phrasing it follows different patterns. A master musician can create an atmosphere of the raga while using these patterns of ornamentations. Similarly, in Western classical music, ornamentation was flourished and were used in Baroque music. *Diruta* Italian organist, music theorist, and composer explains, the significance of ornamentation that were used to play instruments. He suggests that it is expected to play the instrument equally quilled the touch is supposed to be easy and it is important to sustain the harmony. The player needs to occupy the performance with ornaments such as tremolo and trill (Musical ornamentation: Dannreuther, Edward, 1844-1905).

Thus, ornamentation in the two traditions is different in both techniques as well as in structural framework. In Hindustani classical music the ornamentation is essential to maintain the identity of raga and plays crucial part in the creation of raga, in contrast western music ornamentation is significant in decorative and sustaining the melody and harmony. In Hindustani music ornamentation engage with *shruti*, whereas in western it is solely based on equal temperament.

6.4 Composition and Improvisation

Improvisation forms the core of Hindustani classical music. A musician expresses the raga, along with the fundamentals while creating an ambience. Performances often start with a free-flowing *alap* and then gradually introduce rhythm with increasing complexity through *vistar* (melodic expansion), *layakari* (rhythmic variation), *palta* (permutations of pitch sequences), emphasis on target note, and *alankara* motifs, ending with *tahais* (rhythmic cadences). In Hindustani classical music improvisation consists its beauty, when different musical elements are used. For example, *shruti* or using microtones, *meend, kan swara, pakad and vadi, samvadi* (Kaushik Banerjee, K. K. B., Patranabis, A., & Mondal, A. (2023)).

In Western classical music, it is suggested that musicians focus on the accurate articulation of composed music in the initial stage. Western classical music traditionally emphasizes precomposed and notated compositions with limited scope for improvisation. Similarly, it can be only performed by master musician in both traditions and requires advance technical knowledge. They both have different pedagogical priorities: Hindustani classical training cultivates spontaneous melodic creativity within the boundaries of raga, whereas western classical pedagogy focuses on analytical accuracy in written composition and improvisation comes secondary. Hindustani classical music uses extensive use of *shrutis*, in contrast western operates within equal temperament. The pedagogical approach for improvisation, in Hindustani guru shish, and in Western music notation based.

7. Corresponding Terms in Hindustani and Western Classical Music Traditions

The following table represents a comparative overview of terminologies selected from the Hindustani classical music and western music traditions. The comparison is based on Functional analysis rather than direct equiva-

Table 1: Comparison of Hindustani and Western Classical Music Terminology

Hindustani Classical	Western Classical	Explanation
Swara	Note	A discrete musical tone or pitch. Swara is relational whereas Western notes are generally fixed-pitch based. Both refer to distinct pitch units; however, swara functions within a relative pitch system centred on Sa, while Western notes are commonly based on fixed-pitch tuning systems.
Shruti	Microtone	The smallest perceptible pitch interval, offering microtonal variation beyond the Western semitone system. Shruti allows subtle pitch inflections and expressive nuances not typically found in Western scales or modes.
Raga	Mode/Scale	A structured melodic framework defined by prescribed ascending (aroha) and descending (avaroha) movements and specific expressive rules. Unlike Western scales or modes, a raga embodies characteristic melodic patterns, mood, and performance conventions.
Tala	Time Signature/Meter	A cyclical rhythmic framework composed of fixed beats (matra), divided into sections (vibhag), and marked by points such as sam, tali, and khali. Western meter generally follows a linear rhythmic structure, whereas tala is based on cyclical repetition.
Matra	Beat	The basic rhythmic unit in Hindustani music grouped into tala cycles, analogous to a beat in Western meter.
Sam	Downbeat	The first and most emphasized beat of a tala cycle, comparable to the downbeat in Western music.
Khali	Weak Beat	An unstressed beat within a tala cycle, similar to weak beats in Western meter. However, khali serves as both a rhythmic and visual marker within Hindustani cyclical structures.
Laya	Tempo	The speed or pulse of rhythmic flow, indicating whether the performance is slow, medium, or fast.
Vilambhit Laya	Largo/Adagio	A slow tempo corresponding approximately to Largo or Adagio in Western music.
Madhya Laya	Moderato	A medium tempo roughly equivalent to Moderato in Western music.
Drut Laya	Allegro/Presto	A fast tempo comparable to Allegro or Presto in Western music.
Other terms such as aroha, avaroha, tana, alap, jor, bandish, mukhda, jhala, antara, and tihai	Various Western Equivalents	These elements perform introductory, developmental, and rhythmic functions comparable to certain Western musical devices, although the scope and nature of improvisation differ considerably between the two traditions.

lence, appreciating the different theoretical and cultural frameworks of both systems. Comparative framework of fundamental elements in both music forms Hindustani classical music and western music (Rayacaudhuri, V. (2000)).

The comparison shows that several terms in Hindustani and western classical music serve shared and similar functionality in structure and expressive roles, although they arise from different musical philosophies. Therefore, the connection shown in the table should be understood based on functionality rather than exact theoretical matches.

7.1 Explanatory Notes

Shruti (Microtone): Hindustani classical music employs a system of 22 micro-intervals (*shruti*) within the octave, enabling expressive pitch variation different beyond from the Western semitone equal temperaments system. The theoretical basis of this framework is discussed in ancient treatises like *Natyashastra* by *Bharata Muni*.

Tala Structure: Tala consist of systematic cycles, divided into stressed (*tali*) and unstressed (*khali*) portions, with markers such as *sam* and *vibhag* guiding performers and listeners in the Musical practices (Rayacaudhuri, V. (2000)).

7.2 Vocal Techniques in Hindustani and Western Classical Music

Aakar (vocalizing) plays a foundational role in both musical traditions. In Western vocal training, Bel Canto singing related to the mixed voice technique, which allows smooth transitions between all vocal registers. During training, vocalists sustain open vowel sounds such as A,E,I,O, and U, which help to modulate throat movement. Similarly, in Hindustani music, *aakar* practice using *swara* Aa employed to develop resonance and smooth transitions, and breath control, thereby improving tonal clarity during melodic passages. This technique allows the singer to maintain precision without interference from constant articulation. It is particularly effective during rhythmically intensive sections of musical pieces. The difference reveals, that *aakar* in Hindustani classical music plays a central role in developing *alaap* and overall development of the *raga*, whereas in Western music compositions, it primarily serves for technical expression and skills (Nan, Z. (2023)).

Meend (Glissando) In Hindustani classical music, it refers to a continuous, unbroken slide from one note to another and is essential in *raga* performances for sustaining the melody. In Western music, glissando functions as an unusual interpretation in music notation, with its relation to time. Glissando emphasizes sonorous movement, rather than precise pitches, focusing on texture and timbre. Glissando does not necessarily involve microtonal notes. *Meend* incorporates subtle microtonal pitches (*shruti*), each retaining unique identity and its application enhances the emotional expression of the *raga*. Although both provide a smooth transition, *meend* involves microtonal movements essential to the *raga*, in contrast, glissando functions within equal tempered tonal system. It removes linear temporality and allows us to experiment with the infinite possibilities of being outside the time structures (Pratyush. (2010), Terren, M., & Hope, C. (2016)).

Breath Control and Dynamics: Breath control is a core element in both musical traditions. In Western music it is essential for performers to manage the phrases and dynamics during performance. This can be categorized into different types long, short and breath holding breaths. It is directly linked to emotional expression through dynamics similarly in Hindustani classical music involves diaphragmatic breathing and belly breathing to achieve deep resonance while sustaining long phrases specifically in *vilambhit laya*. The key difference lies in function in Hindustani music it directly shapes the development of the *raga*, in contrast to Western music it primarily helps in pre-composed noted phrasing (Joshi. (2022)).

Gamak (Oscillation / Vibrato) *Gamak* produces an

oscillatory effect between notes, adding depth, complexity, and rhythmic weight to the performance. In Western music, vibrato is an important vocal technique, being expressive and frequently used to shape melodies, *gamak* is more structural to Hindustani music and is articulated carefully according to the mood of *raga*. In Western music, vibrato is a vocal technique used to add warmth, richness, emotional depth producing long notes that leaves a lingering impact to the listeners. The key difference lies in structural function: Hindustani classical focuses on single melodic, whereas Western music is based on harmonic structural system involving multiple pitches (Pratyush. (2010)).

8. DISCUSSION / ANALYSIS

8.1 The Influence of Western Music on Indian Music

The influence discussed here is assessed through historically documented collaborations and events, existing musicological scholarships, and stylistic analysis of recordings. Western popular music has significantly impacted Indian music culture, particularly through the process of musical globalization showcased by artists such as *The Beatles* and *Michael Jackson*. These artists transcended national boundaries, captivating global youth audiences and shaping artistic sensibilities across cultures. These artists were selected due to their historically documented roles in cross-cultural musical exchange and their impact on practices across traditions.

George Harrison of *The Beatles* engaged deeply with Indian classical music, notably incorporating the sitar into songs such as "*Norwegian Wood*," "*Love You To*," and "*Within You Without You*," These contributions helped to develop the *raga rock* genre and introduced Indian melodic aesthetics to Western audiences. Harrison's collaboration with sitar maestro Pandit Ravi Shankar was instrumental in showcasing the exchange between Eastern and Western traditions through performances, recordings, and cultural dialogue (Guerrero, R. (2015)).

9. Differences between Hindustani and Western Classical Music Forms

India consists of two principal musical traditions; the northern system is known as Hindustani classical music, and the southern system is recognized as Carnatic music. The northern system emphasizes a monophonic, linear approach centered on *raga* as a fundamental melodic structure. Through solo presentations, it explores musical

complexities using ornamentation and improvisation. In contrast, in Western classical music, harmony is defined by chordal structures and the interdependence of multiple pitches. In Hindustani music, melodic progression and a sustained drone maintain continuity, commonly accompanied by *tanpura*, rather than through harmonic accompaniment.

The tuning approach of these two systems differs significantly. Hindustani music operates within an octave, traditionally conceptualized as comprising 22 *shrutis*, microtonal intervals between *swaras*. This system allows performers to explore microtonal shading, which evokes emotional expression and raga identity. Although modern practice often aligns with a twelve-tone structure, these microtonal elements remain foundational to the performance. In contrast, western classical music operates according to the 12-tone equal temperament system, with fixed semitone intervals and standardized tuning across all instruments. These observations are based on comparative analysis of melodic structure, rhythm, and performance practices in both traditions.

These contrasts can be summarized as follows:

- **Monophonic vs. harmonic:** Hindustani classical music focuses on a single melodic line enhanced by microtonal and rhythmic concepts, whereas Western classical music relies on harmonic interplay and structured progressions.
- **Raga vs. chordal systems:** In Hindustani music, raga defines melodic language through ascent, descent, and emotional palette, whereas Western music provides tonal center and chord progression for overall functioning and modulation.
- **Microtone vs. equal temperament:** Hindustani musical traditions employ flexible microtonal variation that are not fixed or rigidly explained, whereas Western classical music depends on fixed tuning systems, ensuring consistency across compositions.

These structural differences showcase two distinct artistic approaches: one rooted in improvisatory melodic depth and the other in vertical musical organization.

10. Fusion Music and Cross-Cultural Musical Integration: Case Studies

Fusion music refers to a genre in which two or more elements from different traditions are combined. It blends cultural practices, symbols, foundational musical elements,

and expressions from diverse backgrounds to create new music. This concept enhances understanding between different traditions, promotes cross-culture integration and reflects globalization. In this context, fusion showcases the contrasting musical elements between the two traditions. The following case studies demonstrate how different artists have contributed to fusion practices and their adaptation of these elements within distinct cultural expressions. These artists were selected due to their documented engagement in cross-culture collaboration and their influence on the development of fusion music.

Pandit Ram Narayan, a renowned sarangi player, famously remarked, fusion music comes from confusion. The statement reflects the challenges associated with merging diverse musical traditions in context of globalization. The rise of industrialization and globalization, mainstream genres such as hip-hop, jazz, pop, rock, and rock and roll with their catchy melodies and rhythms, became particularly appealing to younger audiences. In contrast, Hindustani classical music, with its complex understanding of raga and tala, appeared less approachable. When these complexities were unfamiliar to a wider audience, they created a barrier to accessibility. Thus, it became a challenge for musicians to sustain classical music in the mainstream (Vedabala, S. (2025)).

According to Percussionist Fazal Qureshi, fusion is often misunderstood in India as most people think, just mixing both musical forms will be fusion. Fusion emerged as a creative blend that highlights both richness of classical music and the modern approach to western music. Debates on fusion often focus on cultural tensions and authenticity. Percussionist Fazal Qureshi highlights the common misinterpretation of fusion music in India, where it often understood merely as simplistic mixing of styles. He further elaborates that, understanding music is fundamental while one engage in creating fusion music. His perspective highlights the importance of respect for both musical forms and cooperation in the process of collaboration. Critics argue that combining classical traditions with other genres may limit the authenticity of raga, decomposing its original characteristics making it impure, this reflects the tension between the preservation, innovation and in the evolution of Indian music.

10.1 Ustad Zakir Hussain: Rhythmic integration

Ustad Zakir Hussain, a *table* maestro, contributed to fusion by incorporating Hindustani tala structures with jazz polyrhythms. These collaborative projects helped him accommodate dialogues within Western ensemble

settings through the adaptation of rhythmic cycles. When his father fell ill, Zakir Hussain was invited to perform internationally for the first time with Pandit Ravi Shankar. During his adolescence, he developed a deep interest in jazz and Western band recordings. He witnessed his first live jazz performance when Duke Ellington visited India and then he performed with his father. This experience shaped his early performances on the West Coast of the United States, marking his entry into the jazz world. He became one of the first *table* maestros to collaborate with jazz artists on such big scale, a groundbreaking development that challenged boundaries (Bhandari, S. (2024)).

10.2 Pandit Ravi Shankar: Musical adaptation between India and West

Pandit Ravi Shankar was a pioneering sitarist who introduced Indian classical music to the western audience through collaboration by numerous projects. Shankar maintained the purity of raga while engaging with western harmonics or orchestral framework rather than just blending both styles. His approach focused on controlled adaptation, where Indian ragas served as the foundation while Shankar experimented with harmonies, blending with Western instrumentation and orchestra. Shankar's performances at major cultural events like Woodstock Festival (1969) reached wider audience, received profound responses, and affirmed his role which became the bridge between India and West (Goswamy, S. (2019)).

10.3 Rishabh Rikhiram Sharma: Contemporary fusion music practices

Rishabh represents a contemporary generation of musicians engaging with fusion through various platforms. His works reflect a synthesis of classical Indian melodies popular musical cultures. Rishabh Sharma is recognized as an emerging figure in fusion music. He played sitar from the age of ten, he established himself as a performing artist by the age of twenty-two. Seamlessly combining sitar with diverse instruments has attracted attention among younger audiences. One of his abilities lies in showcasing classical artistry with a modern sensibility without losing its cultural identity.

This approach prioritizes accessibility while simplifying the complex classical framework to reach and suit contemporary listeners. Collectively, these artists demonstrate innovative strategies reflecting evolving nature of fusion and new levels of musical adaptation.

11. Findings and Conclusion

This study presents a comparative analysis of Hindustani classical music and Western classical music. Although they have distinct cultural backgrounds, philosophical and geographical backgrounds as well as structural frameworks, both traditions share a similar emphasis on melody, rhythm, ornamentation, vocal techniques, and structure. The key findings of the study show that both traditions share functional similarities but differ in their theoretical foundation. Hindustani classical music is based on raga, improvisation, and microtonal elements such as *shrutis*, whereas Western music is based on harmonic organization, structured compositions, and equal temperament. The Western music tradition follows a harmonic texture, whereas Hindustani music establishes a monophonic musical approach. Further, the study highlights rhythmic differences in both systems, showing that Hindustani music follows cyclical rhythmic approach (tala), whereas Western music operates with linear time structures (time signatures). Improvisation plays a crucial role in the Hindustani musical system, whereas Western music aligns with notation-based compositions. Both traditions reveal a parallel approach to musical expressions: Hindustani music emphasizes the significance of rasa, microtones, and ornamentations, whereas western music focuses on dynamics, harmony, and phrasing. They both share similar musical goals: however, they operate within distinct structural systems. In the final section the study analyzes the selected case studies to examine cross-cultural adaptation of fusion practices between both systems.

Authorship contribution

Lavanya Gosai led the research as a significant contributor.

Funding

No funding was taken for conducting this research.

Conflict of interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

Similarity Index

I hereby confirm that there is no similarity index in this research paper is below 10% with no individual source above 2

Declaration

This research has been conducted ethically, reporting of those involved in this article.

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